

PHOSPHATE FUNCTIONALIZED GRAPHENE OXIDE AS ADSORBENT FOR THE REMOVAL OF PB(II) FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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ABSTRACT

Phosphate functionalized graphene oxide (PGO) was prepared by grafting triethyl phosphite onto the surface of graphene oxide (GO) by Arbuzov reaction. The characterization of PGO demonstrated that GO was successfully functionalized by phosphate and the resulting PGO was evaluated as an adsorbent to remove lead from aqueous solution. The experimental results indicated that the PGO showed higher adsorption capacity than GO. The adsorption capacity of PGO was calculated as 236.6 mg/g at 25°C room temperature.

1 INTRODUCTION

Lead is a highly poisonous metal and toxic in nature and it is found mainly in water, air, soil and consumer products. Lead pollution is a major threat for the human health because it is neurotoxic [1] and it induces inflammatory cascades in various tissues [2]. Oral ingestion of lead is an important public health concern [3] because approximately 33% of the absorbed lead in soft tissue is accumulated in liver, kidney and brain. Lead poisoning in blood, with concentration range of 30 to 80 µg/dl, can cause abdominal pain, gastrointestinal colic, intestinal paralysis and constipation. Drinking water is a substantial contributor of lead poisoning in human health. Average of 1-20% of the total diseases caused by lead poisoning in human health is due to lead contaminated drinking water [4]. Research studies have revealed positive correlation between high concentrations of lead in drinking water and raised blood lead level (BLLs) by studies conducted in countries, such as Canada [5], USA [6, 7] and UK [8, 9]. Sources of lead can be from natural origin and anthropogenic activities, such as industrial waste [10], road side soil pollution [11], lead acid battery [12], use of agrochemicals [13], food storage [14] etc. In recent years, Flint water crisis in Michigan has been a debated topic on lead pollution in water that first started in 2014. It affected the residents, specially the children residing in that area [15-17].

Previously various techniques for lead removal have been tested such as electrocoagulation [18], spherical agglomeration technique [19], reduction-melting [20], nanocomposites [21, 22], biosorption [23, 24], electrokinetic technique [25], adsorption columns [26] etc. Removal of heavy metal by adsorption has been of great interest to the researchers. Manawi et al. used acacia gum (AG) to remove lead from contaminated water using polymer-enhanced membrane filtration (PEMF) [27]. The highest adsorption capacity of AG was about 12.2 mg/g when 1000 ppm AG was added to 35 ppm lead solution

at pH 7. Nanoadsorbent fabricated using SnO₂ nanoparticles as core, coated with mesoporous silica and modified with Aminopropyl triethoxysilane was synthesized and tested for lead removal from aqueous solution [22]. A novel nitrogen donor containing ligand of N,N'-di (3-carboxysalicylidene)-3,4-diamino-5-hydroxypyrazole (DSDH) was prepared and it was anchored onto the mesoporous silica by direct approach [28]. The mesoporous silica was used as nano-adsorbent for sensitive detection and selective removal of Pb(II) ions from aqueous media. The maximum adsorption capacity was found as 169.34 mg/g.

Graphene is an allotrope of carbon that consists of a single layer of carbon atoms arranged in a hexagonal lattice. Graphene oxide obtained by treating graphite with strong oxidizers and contains carbon, oxygen and hydrogen in variable ratios. Graphene oxide contains a range of reactive oxygen functional groups that makes it possible to be chemically functionalized and can be used as anchoring sites for metal ion complexation [29]. GO is usually functionalized for its use as adsorbent because it is difficult to separate the GO from water owing to its excellent dispersibility [30]. The advantages of using functionalized GO is that it has high adsorption efficiency and it can be synthesized in various techniques [31]. Zhao et al. used graphene oxide nanosheets to remove Cd(II) and Co(II) from aqueous solution in the presence of humic acid [32]. To remove Hg(II), a decontaminant column packed with nanostructured sulfur-doped porous reduced graphene oxide was used that successfully removed 99.99% of Hg(II) [33].

Graphene oxide has been used in removal of heavy metal in various previous studies. Magnetic MnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles and graphene oxide-MnFe₂O₄ magnetic nanohybrids was synthesized following coprecipitation technique and it was investigated for the core-removal of arsenic and lead contamination from water [34]. The adsorption capacity of GO-MnFe₂O₄ nanohybrids was 673 mg/g and 146 mg/g for Pb(II) and As(III). Graphene and graphene oxide (GO) are ordinary nano-structured adsorbents which suffers from problems due to its structural property, such as hydrophilic surface and aggregation in water. Wei et al. prepared sulfanilic acid modified GO (SGO) via temperate and easily handled method to remove lead from aqueous solution, because SGO can powerfully attract positively charged pollutants [35]. The maximum adsorption capacity of SGO was 2530 mg/g for methylene blue and 415 mg/g for Pb(II). Magnetically responsive chitosan functionalized 3D graphene nanocomposites (MCF3DG), synthesized by one-step self-assembly of graphene sheets, was used to remove lead ions from aqueous solution and the maximum adsorption capacity for Pb(II) is 957.28 mg/g [36]. Liu et al. prepared phosphate-functionalized graphene oxide (PGO) by grafting triethyl phosphite onto the surface of GO following Arbuzov reaction to remove U (VI) from aqueous solution [37]. It has also been proven to be an effective catalyst for three component Biginelli condensation reaction possessing 96% yield under microwave condition [38].

The main objectives of this research is to (1) synthesize graphene oxide following modified Hummer's method and functionalize it by phosphate to make phosphate functionalized graphene oxide (PGO) adsorbent to remove lead from aqueous solution; (2) characterize PGO; (3) assess the lead adsorption capacity of PGO at different initial lead concentrations.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

To synthesize graphene oxide, graphite flakes, sodium nitrate (ReagentPlus®, ≥99.0%), sulfuric acid (98%), potassium permanganate (ACS Reagent ≥99.0%), hydrogen peroxide solution (containing inhibitor, 30 wt. % in H₂O, ACS reagent) were ordered from Sigma-Aldrich. For synthesizing PGO, triethyl phosphite (98%), lithium bromide (ReagentPlus®, ≥99%), tetrahydrofuran (THF) (anhydrous, ≥99.9%, inhibitor-free), N, N-dimethylformamide (DMF) (anhydrous, 99.8%), dichloromethane or methylene chloride (containing 40-150 ppm amylene as stabilizer, ACS reagent, ≥99.5%) were also obtained from Sigma-Aldrich.

2.2 Synthesis of GO

Graphene oxide was prepared by the modified Hummers method from the natural flakes which was oxidized using concentrated H₂SO₄ [32]. First, 4.0 g of graphite flakes were mixed with 300 mL of H₂SO₄ by stirring for overnight at room temperature. The stirring continued for 30 min after the addition

of 3.0 g of NaNO₃ to the reaction mixture. Then the reaction mixture was cooled and kept it below 5°C by using ice bath followed by the slow addition of 18 g of KMnO₄. KMnO₄ has to be added drop wise over the period of 2-3 h. The mixture was stirred for the next 2 h under same conditions. The whole mixture was stirred at 35°C for 48 h to complete the oxidation of the graphite. The solution was transferred to a hot plate stirrer at 90°C. After the mixture reached the temperature of 90°C, 520 mL of DI water was added to the mixture. The mixture was further stirred for 2 h at 90°C. The temperature was reduced to 60 °C, followed by the addition of 12 mL of H₂O₂ and the solution was allowed to cool down to room temperature. The mixture was stirred for another 2 h. The synthesized graphene oxide was centrifuged at 13000 rpm for 5 min and the pellet was collected. The solid phase was re-dispersed in DI water using vigorous stirring and bath ultrasonication for 30 min. GO dispersion was thoroughly washed with 10% HCl three times and ultrasonicated after each wash. Subsequent washing with water were done until the pH of the supernatant was equal to the DI water. The graphene oxide was put in a container and freeze dried at room temperature. After drying, the GO was grinded in the ball mill machine to get GO powder.

2.3 Synthesis of PGO

The synthesis of PGO has been slightly modified from the original literature [39]. In order to make phosphate functionalized graphene oxide, 250 ml of triethylphosphite was added to 250 mg of GO and the mixture was sonicated for 1 h to get a uniform dispersion. Then, 625 mg of LiBr was added to the resulting solution and further sonicated for 30 min. Subsequently, the resulting dispersion was stirred under N₂ atmosphere for 36 h at 150 °C. The dispersion was then centrifuged at 4000 rpm and dried over night at 100 °C. The monolith was further pulverized in a mortar and pestle and re-dispersed in THF solution. This washing step was repeated using THF, water, DMF, and methylene chloride. Washing with water was used to hydrolyze ethoxyl groups to hydroxyl groups to generate phosphate-functionalized graphene oxide. The obtained solid product was dried at 100 °C for 24 h.

2.4 Characterization of G, GO and P-GO

Nitrogen sorption isotherms were investigated on Micromeritics ASAP 2020 (Accelerated Surface Area and Porosimetry System). Specific surface areas of the samples were calculated using the BET equation and pore size distribution (PSD) curves were calculated by the BJH (Barrett–Joyner–Halenda) method using the adsorption branch. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images were taken by using Hitachi S-3000N at 25 kV.

Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectra were obtained in a transmission mode from KBr pellets at room temperature using Jasco 4700 spectrophotometer. The mass ratio of sample to KBr was kept constant at 1:100. The XRD patterns were measured on DIANO 2100E x-ray diffractometer in order to identify the crystalline compounds. The XRD data were taken with 40 kV and 15 mA of X-ray and scanned at 10 deg/min rate. The wavelength of the Cu K α source was 1.540596 Å. The XPS measurements were calculated using Scienta Omicron ESCA 2SR XPS system. The spectra were constructed with monochromatic Al K α X-ray source (hv = 1486.6 eV) operated at 600W with the base pressure of 1 \times 10⁻⁹ mbar in the analysis chamber.

2.4 Batch Adsorption Study

Graphene oxide (GO) and phosphate functionalized GO (PGO) were experimented as adsorbents for lead adsorption from aqueous solution. For the experiment, 100 mL of 50 mg L⁻¹ lead nitrate solution at pH 6.1 was placed in a 250 mL conical flask. After adding the adsorbents, the solutions were placed in a mechanical shaker at 300 rpm for 24 hours at 25°C. The conical flasks were then removed and solutions were filtered using a 0.45 μ m filter paper. The equilibrium concentrations of each solution were measured by Perkin Elmer 800 series atomic absorption spectrometer (AAS). The amount of adsorbed lead at equilibrium, q_e (mg/g) was calculated by using the following equation stated in [40]:

$$q_e = \frac{(C_i - C_f) \times V}{M} \quad (1)$$

Where, q_e is the adsorption capacity (mg/g), C_i and C_f are the liquid-phase initial and final concentration of lead (mg/L), respectively, V is the volume of the solution (L) and M is the mass of adsorbent used (g).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The BET surface area of graphite and graphene oxide (GO) is $0.37 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and $498.15 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, respectively. And after functionalization of GO with phosphate, surface area decreased to $71.47 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. Table 1 shows the textual parameter of GO and PGO. The introduction of phosphate functional groups reduced the BET surface area of GO.

Table 1: Textual parameters of GO and PGO.

Sample	BET Surface Area (m^2/g)	Pore Volume (cm^3/g)	Pore Size (nm)	Nanoparticle size (nm)
GO	498.15	0.293	2.35	12.04
PGO	71.47	0.142	7.92	83.95

As shown in the XRD spectra (Fig. 1), the graphite has a characteristic diffraction peak at 26.50° which conforms to the normal graphite spacing (002) of graphite plane [32]. The peak diminishes in graphene oxide. The diffraction peak of graphene oxide is at $2\theta = 10.52^\circ$ and it is a typical of GO. It indicates the graphitic uniform layered structure [38, 40]. The phosphate functionalized graphene oxide has a broad peak around 23.78° (2θ).

Figure 1: XRD pattern of Graphite(inside box), GO and PGO.

The presence of phosphate was confirmed by comparing the XPS spectrum of GO and PGO. The O1s and C1s peak in the XPS survey spectra of GO and PGO can be seen in Fig. 2 (a) and (b) and the P 2p peak is observed in the XPS survey spectra of PGO. The O1s peak intensity of PGO is lower than that of GO and it is due to the reduction of GO surface during the synthesis of PGO [38]. The C1s XPS spectrum of GO in Figure 2(a) indicates that the graphite flakes was oxidized with different functional groups, i.e. non-oxygenated ring C (284.80 eV, 47.25%), the C atom in C-O (286.04, 29.08%), the carbonyl C (288.82 eV, 19.84%) and the carboxylate carbon (O-C=O) (288.92 eV, 3.83%) [42]. The specific peak area indicated in Fig. 2(c) shows that the main oxygen-containing groups are C-O and C=O and it can form strong surface complexes with Pb (II) on the solid surfaces [32]. The C1s spectrum of PGO also shows the presence of different functional groups, i.e. non-oxygenated ring C (49.27%), C-

OH (33.13%), C=O (10.92%) and C(O)O (5.86%) and a new bond, the C-P bond (0.82%), can be confirmed from the XPS. As the PGO was synthesized by Arbusov reaction at 150 °C, it resulted in the partial removal of hydroxyl and epoxide groups present in GO surface [43]. The high resolution P 2p peak can further be deconvoluted into two spin orbit splitting peaks at 133.21 and 134.40 eV, which corresponds to P-O and P-C binding energy [44]. The deconvoluted O 1s peak of PGO showed binding peaks for CO-OH (25.61%), OH (58%) and C=O (13.75%) at 531.58 eV, 533.34 eV and 536.06 eV respectively. The presence of P-O bonding was confirmed by the peak at 533.98 eV.

Figure 2: XPS survey spectra of (a) GO, (b) PGO, C 1s XPS spectra of (c) GO, (d) PGO, (e) O 1s XPS spectra of PGO, (f) P 2p XPS spectra of PGO.

Fig. 3 shows the FT-IR spectra of GO and absorption peaks of the stretching mode of C=O, aromatic C=C, carboxyl O=C-O, epoxy C-O, alkoxy C-O are at 1725 cm^{-1} , 1620 cm^{-1} , 1401 cm^{-1} , 1111 cm^{-1} and 1081 cm^{-1} , respectively. The broad peak between 2500 cm^{-1} and 3750 cm^{-1} is assigned to -OH stretching vibration [34, 44-46]. The peak at 1224 cm^{-1} and 1729 cm^{-1} is associated with P=O stretching and it confirms the presence of phosphate functional groups. The new peaks related to phosphate functional groups appeared in the PGO, such as a sharp peak at 1222 cm^{-1} and 931 cm^{-1} which are associated with P=O and P-O stretching [48].

Figure 3: FT-IR Spectrum of GO and PGO.

To characterize the morphologies of graphite and prepared graphene oxide, the samples were characterized by SEM images. From the SEM images of graphite flakes in Fig. 4(a,b) it is observed that it has smooth and defined layered surfaces. Higher magnification micrographs indicate smaller particles of graphite flakes. The SEM images of graphene oxide in Fig. 4(c,d) shows crumpled and rippled surfaces similar to observations reported in [35, 48]. The graphene oxide does not have any pattern. The

graphene oxide has wrinkled surface as compared to graphite flakes. The morphology of PGO can be examined in Fig. 4 (e,f) and it shows flower-like phosphate groups evenly distributed onto the graphene oxide powder. The images are similar to the images found in other literatures [37, 38, 49]. EDX spectrum in PGO shows strong peak of phosphate that confirms the functionalization of GO with phosphate. The elemental analysis shows that percentages of carbon, oxygen and phosphate are 61.75, 30.35 and 7.95 respectively. The EDX elemental mapping in Fig. 5 shows that phosphate is evenly distributed onto the surface of GO.

Figure 4: SEM image of (a, b) Graphite flakes, (c,d) GO and (e,f) PGO

Figure 5: EDX elemental phosphorus Mapping of PGO.

Figure 6: N₂ Adsorption-desorption curve of (a) GO and (c) PGO. The insets shows the pore size distribution for (b) GO and (d) PGO.

N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherm of both GO and PGO in Fig. 6 shows low pressure hysteresis which is indicative of layered structure of the adsorbent, and also of under-equilibrated data. Under equilibrated data is due to the narrow/constricted micropore volume network development and there was not enough time for the nitrogen to diffuse into/out of the micropore volume. The knee of the isotherm for PGO is less distinctive and it is an indication of a significant amount of overlap of monolayer coverage [50]. The open hysteresis loop could be attributed to the layered structure of GO and PGO.

5 ADSORPTION BEHAVIOUR

Adsorption behavior of GO and PGO was experimented at different initial concentration of Pb(II). The adsorbent dosage was 0.33 g/L, the contact time was 24 hours and the temperature was 25°C. The volume of the Pb(II) was 30 mL and after putting the adsorbent, the solution was put inside a mechanical shaker at a shaking speed of 300 rpm. The adsorption capacities were experimented at initial concentration of Pb(II) 29.71 mg/L, 44.19 mg/L, 102.2 mg/L and 191.3 mg/L. The results indicates that PGO has higher adsorption capacity for lead than GO. At an initial concentration of 102.2 mg/L, GO and PGO has 191.92 mg/g and 229.39 mg/g of lead adsorption capacity respectively and the difference in adsorption capacity between these two adsorbents is the highest at this initial concentration. Significant improvement in Pb(II) adsorption capacity was observed for GO after phosphate functionalization and it could be attributed to the presence of C-P bond in PGO, which was confirmed based on the XPS spectra for GO and PGO.

Figure 7: Adsorption Capacity of GO and PGO at different initial concentrations of lead in aqueous solution. (Experimental conditions: temperature = 25°, contact time = 24 hours, pH = 4.0, adsorbent dosage = 0.33 g/L).

9 CONCLUSIONS

In this research, phosphate functionalized GO was employed as an adsorbent for lead from water. The PGO had low surface area than GO but greater adsorption capacity than GO. It makes it very convenient when using it as an adsorbent for lead. Also due to the very small particle size, GO is very difficult to remove from but PGO solves this problem. PGO showed greater adsorption capacity than GO in all initial concentration. But PGO showed greater adsorption capacity at lower initial concentration of lead. The adsorption results suggest that PGO can be a potential adsorbent for lead from water.

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